

High V_{oc} upon KF post deposition treatment for ultrathin single-stage co-evaporated Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ solar cells

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Abstract

A simplified Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) solar cell structure based on a 500 nm thin CIGS layer is presented. The absorber layers are grown with a single-stage co-evaporation process and various KF post deposition treatments (KF-PDT) are performed. The KF-PDT leads to an efficiency increase from 7% to 12%. For all cells an increase in open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor is measured, which is attributed to an improved pn junction. By changing the annealing conditions an additional V_{oc} increase is measured. This increase is attributed to the reduction of light induced defects at the CIGS/CdS interface in addition to the improved pn junction. A reduction of defects is confirmed by reduced sub band gap emission in the photoluminescence spectra, an increased decay time and increased quasi fermi level splitting. With SCAPS the results are simulated and it is concluded that after KF-PDT the V_{oc} is limited to 640 mV due to recombination at the back contact. A higher V_{oc} can then only be achieved by applying a passivation layer at the back. There are no indications that the single-stage process is limiting the efficiency revealing the potential of the proposed simplified CIGS structure and the importance of interfaces for ultrathin CIGS solar cells.

Keywords: solar cells, thin films, Cu(In,Ga)Se₂, photoluminescence, KF-PDT

Introduction

Thin film Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) solar cells are a well-established marketable thin film technology. It has the highest conversion efficiencies of the different inorganic thin film technologies for both solar cells and modules.¹ However, to really implement CIGS on the scale of the robust Si technology and compete with it, the production of CIGS solar cells has to reduce in costs. There are several roads towards achieving this cost reduction. Obviously increasing the efficiency is the most important step towards that objective. Efficiencies beyond 22% have been achieved by implementing various alkali treatments and optimizing Ga and/or S gradients at the front and back.^{2,3} However, making these elemental gradients in the absorber layer makes the process complicated to implement on large scale, and often several steps are required to achieve this. Another explored road towards cost reduction is decreasing the thickness of the absorber layer. This also reduces the occurrence of In shortage on the long term. However, when going to thin CIGS layers the interfaces become limiting the efficiency and passivation is required.⁴ Passivation for thin CIGS at the back contact is in an exploration state, but good results have already been achieved by using a steep Ga gradient at the back and dielectric passivation layers.^{5,6} The absorber layer itself however, might need less restrictive requirements, since the diffusion length of the minority carriers does not have to be as long as for the thick layers. This opens opportunities to investigate simpler and faster absorber layer growth processes. Our aim is to investigate the potential of a simplified CIGS solar cell structure using a thin CIGS absorber layer without any elemental front or back gradients. The thickness of the absorber layer is decreased to around 500 nm, which should be thick enough to absorb all light after total reflection at the back

contact. One way to produce this simpler absorber layer is using a single-stage co-evaporation step. Earlier research has shown only a very small difference between single-stage and 3-stage co-evaporated CIGS solar cells and the authors concluded that they had very similar electrical properties.⁷ However, in that specific case, the single-stage processed absorber layer still had a Ga gradient and was 2 μm thick. For thinner layers this difference in efficiency might become even smaller. The difference in processing single and 3-stage absorber layers is the lack of a copper rich stage for the single-stage process. In the single-stage process all elements are deposited with the same evaporation rate, while for the 3-stage process the evaporation rate of the metals are varied, leading to a temporary copper rich state during the growth, and a longer evaporation time.⁷ During the copper rich stage the grain size increases and planar defects inside the grain are annihilated.⁸ Thus, without a copper rich step the absorber layer has small grains with planar defects. The planar defects must cause electronic defect states, though clear understanding of the effect on device performance has not been achieved yet. When the grain size decreases unavoidably the number of grain boundaries increases. Grain boundaries in CIGS are considered to be rather benign, though from modelling it has been shown that when the grains are too small, the efficiency deteriorates.⁹ The smaller grains are also considered to be one of the causes for the lower efficiency with increasing Ga content.¹⁰ Nevertheless, the precise impact of the grain boundaries is still under discussion. It has been shown though, that alkali metals change the electronic structure beneficially and reduce any recombination at the grain boundaries.¹¹⁻¹³ Alkali treatments in general have positive impact on solar cells performance and are responsible for record efficiencies.¹⁴ The most recent improvements are related to the heavier alkali like K and Rb, of which K has proven to be beneficial for the pn junction properties. This is especially interesting for thin CIGS layers, since the interfaces become more limiting for thinner absorber layers. The mechanisms behind the improvements due to KF post deposition treatment (KF-PDT) are still under investigation, but there are several common findings. It is known that K depletes the surface from copper resulting in a surface band gap widening.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ The surface band gap widening in its turn results in an improved pn junction and quenched recombination.^{18,19} This depletion of Cu may also happen at the grain boundaries and thereby improve the quality of the absorber layer.¹² Direct improvement of bulk properties by reduction of bulk defects and increased carrier collection in the bulk measured with EBIC, have been observed as well.^{20,21} From photoluminescence measurements on absorber layers it has been shown that KF treatment reduces also potential fluctuations.²² All these findings are based on devices and thick absorber layers that are grown by 3-stage co-evaporation and a PDT in Se environment. In the work of Zahedi-Azhed thick single-stage absorber layers are used as well, though no further explanation is given on the differences between the single and 3-stage absorber layers.¹⁹ Results of KF-PDT on CIGS layer processed otherwise are limited. Initial results of KF-PDT on thin single-stage absorber layers are published by de Wild and Hsu has performed KF-PDT on sputtered CIGS layers, both showing improved device efficiency.^{23,24} Additionally, the PDT in both studies was done without added Se. Harel has performed KF-PDT under S atmosphere and this led to improved devices as well.²⁵ At last, changing the buffer layer, i.e. using a Zn(O,S) instead of CdS buffer layer, or deposition of a KInSe layer directly also have

shown to benefit the device properties.^{3,26,27} Generally, any form of K addition after absorber layer growth has led to device improvements independent on the annealing atmosphere or the buffer layer. The main requirement for improvements upon K treatment seems to be the presence of a copper poor surface layer.²⁸⁻³⁰ However, even when K is applied before absorber layer growth and reduces the grain size, improvements are observed.³¹ Hence, the precise impact of K in CIGS is still under investigation.

In this contribution we investigate the effect of KF-PDT in nitrogen atmosphere on 500 nm thin single-stage co-evaporated absorber layers by varying the annealing conditions. Devices are prepared and a maximum efficiency of 11.6% with a very high V_{oc} of 668 mV is measured. We found that this V_{oc} is reached due to reduction of light induced defects that are commonly responsible for a V_{oc} drop of tens of mV in thin film solar cells. This increase is in addition to the already improved pn junction. The absorber layers are characterized with glow discharge optical emission spectroscopy (GDOES), grazing incidence XRD (GI-XRD), room temperature and temperature dependent photoluminescence (PL) and time resolved PL (TRPL). For the PL analysis a 3-stage sample is prepared to compare with the single-stage sample, since we found single-stage specific features in the spectra. We observe a large reduction of sub band gap emission upon KF-PDT for the single-stage absorber layers, indicating reduction of defects. We conclude that after optimized KF treatment the V_{oc} is limited by back surface recombination, not by the absorber layer, and thus further improvements require passivation of the back contact.

2. Methods

CIGS absorber layers are prepared by a single-stage co-evaporation step onto soda lime glass/Si(O, N)/Mo substrates at 550 °C. The Si(O,N) layer suffice as alkali barrier and hence the alkali in the absorber layer are controlled by externally adding them. The elemental fluxes are stabilized before opening the shutter and a constant flux of elements reaches the surface. Deposition takes 7.5 minutes resulting in a layer thickness of just below 500 nm. Na is added prior to the CIGS deposition by sublimating a 2 nm thick NaF layer at room temperature in the vacuum chamber of the co-evaporation tool onto the Mo. The composition and thickness of the CIGS layers are measured with X-ray fluorescence. The $[Cu]/([In] + [Ga])$ ratios vary between 0.79 and 0.91, the $[Ga]/([Ga]+[In])$ ratios between 0.29-0.34 and the thicknesses between 450 and 500 nm. The KF-PDT is done by spincoating solutions of KF with different molarities, varying from 0.1 to 0.4 M, onto the absorber layer followed by a post anneal in N_2 atmosphere for 20 minutes 400 °C. Details can be found in de Wild.²³ Directly after the post anneal, CdS layers are deposited by chemical bath deposition. Absorber layers without KF also underwent the post anneal and served as references. Few absorber layers are prepared of which one half underwent KF treatment and the other half only the post anneal. Those are used for GDOES, GI-XRD and temperature dependent PL measurements. The PL and time resolved PL (TRPL) measurements are done in a photospectrometer from Picoquant with a TimeHarp 260 single photon counter for the time resolved measurements. The excitation intensity was approximately 0.1 Wcm^{-2} , repetition rate 3 MHz, and wavelength 532 nm. One sample is measured in a cryostat from 77 K to room

temperature. The absorber layers are finished into solar cells with sputtered i-ZnO/AZO window layers and evaporated Ni/Al/Ni grids. Samples are 5×5 or 2.5×5 cm² and cells of 0.5 cm² are mechanically scribed. The solar cells are characterized with current-voltage (JV) measurements. The number of the characterized cells varied from 4 (on 2.5×5 cm² substrates) to maximum 10 (on 5×5 cm² substrates). Cells that have FF < 50% are automatically excluded to avoid incorporation of shunted cells, except for one sample that had on average lower FF. With a matlab routine J_0 , shunt and series resistances are determined from the dark JV measurement. With capacitance-voltage measurements the apparent net acceptor concentrations are determined (2 cells for each sample). SCAPS is used to simulate the results and measured resistances and doping concentration are used as input.

Results and discussion

3.1. Absorber layer composition

Absorber layers are prepared for GDOES, GI-XRD and PL measurements under cryogenic conditions, of which one part underwent KF-PDT and another part only the post-anneal. During the post anneal the layers are either covered by a cleaned Mo substrate or exposed to the nitrogen atmosphere, which will be referred to as ‘covered’ or ‘exposed’, respectively. When covered, the substrate is laying on top of the absorber layer leaving negligible distance between the cover and absorber layer. Figure 1 presents a schematic overview of the annealing process and Table 1 the sample matrix.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the KF-PDT. Left: absorber layer is completely covered and hence not exposed to the N₂ flow. Right: absorber layer is exposed to the N₂ flow.

Table 1. Sample matrix of the different KF-PDTs. The Na was supplied prior to CIGS growth. An empty cell means that the sample is not prepared and a small dash - means there is no KF supplied. The concentration is given in molarities (M). Approximately 2 ml solution was spincoated on the 5x5 cm² absorber layer. All samples underwent the post anneal.

Absorber characterization		Solar cells	
Exposed KF supply (M)	Covered KF supply (M)	Exposed KF supply (M)	Covered KF supply (M)
-	-	-	-
0.2	0.2	0.1	0.08
		0.2	0.15
		0.4	0.3

The GDOES profiles of KF treated and untreated exposed and covered absorber layers are measured. The results of the exposed KF treated and untreated samples are presented in Figure 2a and b. We find no differences for the Cu, In, Ga and Se profiles between the KF treated and untreated absorber layers, see Figure 2a. There is no Ga gradient and this remains so after KF treatment. Similar results are found for the covered absorber layers, not shown here. The alkali are presented in Figure 2b. We find that Na is increasing towards the back and K is virtually absent before KF treatment. After KF treatment, Na is virtually absent and K is increasing towards the back (red line). The replacement of Na by K is confirmed by other studies.^{18,32} When we compare the alkali profile of the exposed annealed sample with the covered annealed sample we find that the covered sample has more K at the front (blue line) and reduced amount of Na (S1). The lower K amount for the exposed post anneal might be related to the formation of volatile K species.³³ It is likely that between the CIGS absorber and the cover a local Se/K₂Se atmosphere is created that prevents the escape of K from the sample. This local atmosphere is absent when the absorber layer is exposed, allowing K to escape via the formation of volatile K species.

The GDOES does not exclude formation of secondary phases, only that they are not agglomerated at the front or back. Hence, GI-XRD ($\theta = 0.5^\circ$) is also performed on the two exposed samples with and w/o KF. Figure 2c presents the diffractogram measured for the exposed KF treated and untreated single stage co-evaporated absorber layers. All peaks can be assigned to CIGS with a GGI of 0.3, Mo and MoSe₂. There are no differences between the two samples, implying there is no significant amount (below the detection limit) of secondary phases in the absorber present with

and w/o KF treatment and neither In/Ga segregation. The sharp increase in intensity at 25° can be explained by planar defects that appear during copper poor growth.⁸ The inset presents the 112 peak for single-stage copper rich and copper poor grown absorber layers showing that this increase at 25° is indeed due to the copper poor growth. Besides the planar defects we also find that the peak is much wider for the copper poor grown absorber layer which can be related to the grainsize. They are significantly smaller compared to copper rich grown samples.^{7,8} We conclude from the GI-XRD and GDOES measurement that there are no changes in Ga profile or In-Ga segregation, and that the covered samples have more K at the front of the absorber layer. Local compositional fluctuations or formation of K related phases (Cu, K)InSe₂ that are beyond the detection limit might be present as well.^{15,34}

Figure 2. a) top and bottom GDOES profiles of KF treated and reference absorber layers. b) GDOES profiles of the alkali elements for untreated and KF treated absorber layers. Except for the K there are no differences found between the covered and exposed layers. c) GI-XRD diffractogram of thin single-stage absorber layers with and without KF treatment. The inset presents the 112 peak for copper rich vs copper poor single stage growth. The reference spectra are made with powdercell (C) for GGI of 0.3 (PDF 35-1102) and Mo (PDF 42-1120).

3.2. Photoluminescence

Room temperature PL spectra are recorded of the absorber layers presented in Table 1 and of the covered samples prepared for solar cells, prior to processing them further into solar cells. At room temperature we can expect that donors and acceptors are all active and emission comes from the band edges for ideal materials.³⁵ However, real materials are not ideal and emission can come from states below the band gap as well. We first compare the PL spectra of the single-stage absorber layer with a thin 3-stage sample with similar composition and thickness. The results are presented in Figure 3a. The 3-stage PL spectra can be fitted with one broad Gaussian peak and one sharper Gaussian peak, with similar positions of the peak maxima. We attribute the broader Gaussian peak to broadening due to tail states and local band gap fluctuations. The exact shape of the tail states depends on the origin of the sub band gap absorption, and we did not attempt to fit the peak with a specific sub band gap profile.³⁶ Hence the Gaussian fits are more a guide to the

eye. When we look at the spectra of the single-stage sample, there is clearly an additional peak below the band gap. We attribute this peak to a defect band related to the copper poor growth. At higher energy the peak has a shape similar to the 3-stage sample and consists of one broad and one sharper Gaussian peak, albeit broadened compared to the 3-stage sample. We also measured the single-stage sample at lower temperature, and the results are presented in Figure 3b. The spectra seem different, but that is because the laser excitation intensity is lower in the cryostat and the peak shape is highly dependent on the excitation intensity. We find that the higher energy peak disappears completely with decreasing temperature. This is expected when the emission comes from the band edge. The low energy peak is increasing in intensity and shifted to lower energies, which corresponds to emission from a defect and excludes that it is coming from the band edge of a secondary phase. Hence, we attribute the low energy emission peak to a defect state and the higher energy peaks to the band edge emission of one single phase.

One part of the single-stage sample discussed above underwent KF treatment. The room temperature spectra of the KF treated and untreated sample are presented Figure 3c. We find that the low energy emission is largely decreased after KF treatment, resulting in a sharper high energy peak, very similar to the 3-stage sample. We didn't observe these changes upon KF treatment for the 3-stage sample in the room temperature PL spectra. Though, decrease of sub band gap emission has previously been reported for 3-stage samples when measured at cryogenic temperatures, and it was attributed to the reduction of potential fluctuations following the KF treatment.^{22,37} It is not clear whether the KF treatment affects the single-stage specific defect. To really conclude in detail on the origin of the low energy peak in the single-stage spectra and the effect of the KF treatment on the sub band gap emission, the peaks need to be disentangled which requires more advanced characterization like intensity variations and lower temperatures.³⁵ We conclude that the KF treatment reduces the sub band gap emission and therefore the defects related to this emission.

The reduction of the sub band gap emission with KF treatment comes with an increase in PL yield of 1 to 2 orders. We measured the covered annealed samples (w/o KF, 0.08 M KF, 0.15 M KF and 0.3 M KF) before they were further processed into solar cells at several positions to estimate an increase in V_{oc} from the intensity increase compared to the reference sample. It is known that the absolute PL yield is a measure for the quasi fermi level splitting and can be described with the Lasher-Stern-Würfel equation:^{38,39}

$$I_{PL}(h\nu) = \frac{2\pi}{h^3 c^2} \frac{(h\nu)^2 a(h\nu)}{\exp\left(\frac{h\nu - \Delta\mu}{kT}\right) - 1} \quad (1)$$

The PL yield is thus a function of the photon energy $h\nu$, the absorptivity $a(h\nu)$ and exponentially dependent on the quasi fermi level splitting $\Delta\mu$. The $\Delta\mu$ itself is a measure for the maximum V_{oc} and any changes can be related to a V_{oc} increase or decrease.⁴⁰ The $\Delta\mu$ changes upon the doping concentration, but also defects in the band gap. Considering that the absorptivity $a(h\nu)$ above the band gap is 1, $\Delta\mu$ is much smaller than $h\nu$ and kT is small, equation (1) can be reduced for emission above the band gap to:

$$I_{PL}(E) = \frac{2\pi}{h^3 c^2} (h\nu)^2 \exp\left(\frac{\Delta\mu - h\nu}{kT}\right) \quad (2)$$

When the peak maxima of the different samples are at the same position, the increase in $\Delta\mu$ between the samples can then be written as:

$$\Delta\mu_{KF-ref} = kT \cdot \ln\left(\frac{I_{KF}}{I_{ref}}\right) \quad (3)$$

with I_{KF} and I_{ref} the peak heights of the fitted highest energy peaks (dashed-dotted peaks). The above determined $\Delta\mu_{KF-ref}$ can then be related to a predicted V_{oc} increase compared to the untreated absorber layer. We calculated this value for the covered absorber layers treated with different KF molarities and the results can be found in Figure 3d (round symbols). We find a maximum $\Delta\mu_{KF-ref}$ of 170 meV, which is equivalent to a V_{oc} increase of 170 mV. We also observe that the increase in $\Delta\mu_{KF-ref}$ seems to saturate for the higher amount of KF. If the improvements due to KF-PDT are only related to the absorber/CdS layer, we can expect a V_{oc} improvement of about 170 mV compared to the reference. Deviations of this value are then attributed to the band bending when the pn junction is formed after deposition of the window layers.³⁰ The TRPL of the emission peaks are measured at each position as well. Since the TRPL decays are measured under low injection concentration it is very likely influenced by trapping and we have to fit the decays with 3 exponentials.⁴¹ The fastest decay time is considered to come from diffusion of the carriers and is around 1 ns.⁴² This corresponds well to our fitted values of around 1 ns for the fast decay. The tail decay is several 10s of ns and is due to trapping. The slightly faster decay of a few ns is then likely the most reliable parameter for the lifetime of the free carriers, albeit still influenced by the other decay times. Figure 3d (squared symbols) presents the average value of this extracted decay time vs the molarity. We find that the extracted decay time follows the trend of the $\Delta\mu_{KF-ref}$ and seems to saturate with increasing KF molarity as well. Based on the PL measurements and decay times we can anticipate a maximum V_{oc} increase of up to 170 mV and saturation for higher molarities.

Figure 3. a) Room temperature PL spectra of a thin single-stage and 3-stage sample. The single-stage sample reveals an additional peak at lower energies. b) Temperature dependent PL spectra of the single-stage sample. The high energy peaks decrease and the low energy peak shifts to lower energy. c) Room temperature PL spectra for single-stage KF treated and untreated samples. The sub band gap emission reduces upon KF treatment. d) Deduced $\Delta\mu_{\text{KF-ref}}$ (equation 3) and average decay time vs. KF molarity.

3.3. Solar cells

Solar cells are prepared from the absorber layers that underwent the various KF treatments given in Table 1. Up to 10 cells are measured and average V_{oc} and FF values with their standard deviations are presented in Figure 4. Since the current is mainly affected by the CIGS layer thickness as we also have shown in our previous paper, we have left these out.²³ Values for J_{sc} can be found in S2. Figure 4a presents the V_{oc} and Figure 4b the FF. The measured values from the exposed cells are plotted in red triangles and from the covered cells in blue squares. For the exposed cells we find a steady increase in V_{oc} from ~ 550 mV to approximately ~ 600 mV and in FF from 57 % to 63 % with increasing amount of KF. For the covered cells the V_{oc} increases from ~ 460 mV to ~ 640 mV and seems to saturate around 640 mV and the FF increases from 52 % to 64 %. Both the V_{oc} increase (~ 180 mV) as well as the saturation correspond well with the deduced $\Delta\mu_{\text{KF-ref}}$ of ~ 170 meV. The V_{oc} increase is thus due to increased quasi fermi level splitting and is

not directly related to the band bending that appears with the formation of the pn junction after window layer deposition.

There are a few noticeable differences between the covered and exposed cells. At first, the reference (w/o KF) of the covered cells has a much lower V_{oc} (~ 460 mV) compared to exposed cells (~550 mV). This could be due to the local Se atmosphere created between the CIGS layer and the cover. It has been shown that the efficiency can deteriorate under Se atmosphere when there are alkali in the absorber layer.⁴³ This could apply in the present case since we add Na before CIGS deposition. Secondly, we find larger standard deviations for the covered samples, compared to the exposed ones. We believe that this indicates that the changes are very sensitive to the K amount at the front. The spincoating process leads to a relatively inhomogeneous lateral distribution of K. When the absorber layers are exposed during the anneal, K can evaporate resulting in a more homogenous lateral K distribution. Subsequently, the variation in the device parameters become smaller for the exposed absorber layers. When the absorber layers are covered, the K distribution is closer to the spincoated amount and thus rather inhomogeneous. This observation strongly suggests that the V_{oc} is very sensitive to the exact amount of K. This can also explain the large steps between the average V_{oc} values for the 0.08 M and 0.15 M KF samples. The last observation is the higher average V_{oc} value of the covered cells compared to the exposed cells for similar amount of added KF. This could be attributed to the higher amount of K at the front after the anneal as measured with GDOES. However, another explanation could be that the formation of a thin (Cu,K)InSe₂ phase known to form on top of the CIGS layer requires a Se atmosphere.^{15,34} Then without the cover this phase is not (completely) formed, while with the cover this phase is formed and covers the surface, resulting in the higher V_{oc} .

To elaborate further on the V_{oc} improvements, the J_0 s, shunt and series resistances are determined from the dark current voltage (JV) measurements of the samples with the highest efficiency for both the exposed and covered cells and their reference (w/o KF). We didn't find any changes in shunt and series resistances, which could explain FF improvement and hence the improvement comes from improved carrier collection. This is accompanied by a steeper slope in the EQE for longer wavelength, which can be seen for the covered KF treated cells compared to the reference (S3). The J_0 decreased with the KF treatment up to one order of magnitude, see Figure 4c. The large variations for the covered absorber layers are visible here as well. We observe that the J_0 values after KF treatment are slightly larger for the covered cells than for the exposed cells even though the V_{oc} is higher (640 vs 600 mV). We can attribute this seeming inconsistency to changes in light induced defects. The J_0 is determined from the dark and gives the maximum V_{oc} when shifted by J_{sc} only if the superposition is fulfilled. However, when there are light induced defects, the V_{oc} is lower than what could be expected from the dark curve. This results in a dark/light crossover, which is commonly observed in thin film solar cells.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹ The most common explanation for this light dependent effect is the presence of defects in the CdS layer or at the CIGS/CdS interface.^{45,46,49}

Figure 4. Device parameters extracted from JV measurements. a) V_{oc} and b) FF for exposed and covered KF-PDT vs spincoated KF molarity. c) J_0 extracted from the dark curves of the most efficient samples (0.15 M KF covered, 0.4 M KF exposed) and their reference.

To determine whether there are changes in light dependent defects upon covered KF treatment, we shift the dark curves by J_{sc} and compare these with the illuminated JV curve. Figure 5 presents the results for an exposed reference cell w/o KF, an exposed KF-PDT cell and a covered KF-PDT cell. The efficiencies were 7.2%, 9.5% and 11.6% for the reference, exposed and covered cell respectively. We find that the measured V_{oc} and FF are always lower than expected from the dark measurement. For the covered cell though, this reduction is marginal, especially in the case of the V_{oc} , resulting in a V_{oc} of 668 mV. For the exposed as well as the reference, we find a reduction of about 70 and 100 mV under illumination respectively. This limits the V_{oc} of the exposed cell to 605 mV despite the higher V_{oc} expected from the shifted dark curve or lower J_0 . It implies that having the KF-treatment while covered affects CIGS surface and corresponding CdS layer growth in a more beneficial way than when the KF treatment is performed under the exposed nitrogen atmosphere. It has to be mentioned that the local atmosphere created under the cover is only beneficial when there is K. We found that the covered reference has a reduced V_{oc} , FF, and correspondingly J_0 .

Figure 5. a) JV curves of exposed untreated and b) KF treated solar cells. The V_{oc} is reduced under light in similar way for both KF treated and untreated solar cells. c) JV curves of exposed treated solar cells: V_{oc} losses under illumination are heavily reduced, resulting in almost complete overlap between dark shifted and light curve and the highest V_{oc} .

To have a closer look at the pn junction, the cells are illuminated under blue light only. This is achieved by letting the light of the solar simulator pass through a 400 nm band pass filter with 20 nm bandwidth and OD4 up to 1200 nm from Thorland. Approximately 50% is absorbed in the CdS layer and the penetration depth in CIGS is 30 nm. Most carriers are thus generated close to the pn junction. The resulting current is about $2 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. To compare these results with the full spectrum we used OD filters to achieve similar current densities. The JV curves measured with blue light only and under OD filters of both KF treated and untreated cells are presented in Figure 6a. There is no difference in the V_{oc} between the blue and neutral light for both the untreated and the KF-treated cells. We find that the JV-curves of the KF treated cells are overlapping, while the sample that had no KF treatment reveal a difference at negative bias. Under blue light a strong non-ohmic shunt is visible, which is less significant under neutral light. Non-ohmic shunts can have several origins, of which tunneling at the CdS/CIGS interface due to high concentration of deep defects and shunts along grain boundaries are the most likely candidates.⁵⁰ Since it is more severe under blue light and related to the KF treatment, we think it comes from tunneling at CdS/CIGS junction. Similar results are obtained for the covered cells as well. Hence, we conclude that the largest improvements upon KF-PDT are due to an improved pn junction, for both exposed and covered cells, but for the covered cells the V_{oc} is improving even more due to a decrease in light induced defects.

After the optimized KF-PDT we observe an average maximum V_{oc} of about 640 mV. This maximum has been confirmed by at least three more samples. For a thin (<500 nm CIGS) layer this is a very high V_{oc} , even when compared to back passivated cells which hold a maximum V_{oc} of ~ 650 mV for a (Ga)/((In) + (Ga)) (GGI) ratio of 0.3.^{4,51} However, KF-treatment of thicker layers have led to a V_{oc} above 700 mV.^{2,3} We attribute this difference to recombination at the back contact and it again reveals the importance of the interfaces when thinning the CIGS layer to 500 nm. Since we have reached a maximum V_{oc} after KF treatment, we investigate the effect of the

back recombination using SCAPS. We used parameters for interfaces and CdS found in a CIGS simulations paper by Frisk.⁵² When using these parameters and our measured doping levels (determined from capacitance-voltage measurements, see S4), thickness and resistances (from dark JV measurements, see S5), the simulation resulted in a maximum V_{oc} of 631 mV, which is close to our average maximum. To find the effect of the back contact on the V_{oc} , we varied the back surface recombination velocity (S_b) for electrons. However, since the V_{oc} is also highly dependent on the doping, we varied the doping as well. The results are presented in Figure 6b. The 640 mV border which is achieved with our optimized KF-PDT is thickened. We have doping values (N_A) around $(3-5) \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ after KF treatment, which indicates that the S_b is of the order of 10^5 cm/s or higher. These are reasonable values for an unpassivated back contact.⁵³ When increasing the doping further we find that it will only marginally increase the V_{oc} further. To really reach a V_{oc} of about 700 mV or higher, marked by the blue line, we find that the S_b has to be reduced to far below 10^4 cm s^{-1} depending on the doping. This can only be achieved by passivation. We therefore conclude that after the optimized KF-treatment, passivation is the main road to achieve higher V_{oc} and that the V_{oc} is limited by the back surface recombination.

Figure 6. a) JV curves under neutral density filters and blue light. A change in non-ohmic shunts is detected for the untreated sample under blue light, while for the KF-treated sample the curves are similar. b) V_{oc} values simulated with SCAPS for KF treated solar cells for various doping N_A and back surface recombination velocities S_b . The thick dark grey line represents the 640 mV border, which is experimentally achieved with the optimized KF-PDT. The thick blue line represents the 700 mV border, showing that this can only be achieved with a low S_b which requires back surface passivation.

4. Conclusion

KF treatment in N_2 atmosphere is performed on thin single-stage CIGS absorber layers. We varied the amount of KF and the exposure of the absorber layer to the N_2 atmosphere during the PDT. We achieved this by covering the absorber layer or by leaving it exposed to the N_2 flow. GDOES measurements revealed no significant differences between the KF treated and untreated

samples and covered/uncovered samples. That means, there are no changes in Ga gradient or In/Ga segregation due to the KF-PDT. For the K though, we found a slightly higher K signal at the front for the covered samples. The photoluminescence spectra revealed significant changes upon KF treatment, namely a large increase in PL yield and decay time combined with a large decrease of the sub band gap emission. This decrease is attributed to passivation or reduction of sub band gap states with the KF treatment. Improvements of the device parameters V_{oc} and FF are observed for all different post anneal treatments. It is worth mentioning that the KF deposition is done ex-situ in air. The air exposure is considered to deteriorate FF, which is not what we have observed.^{16,30} We always have an increase in FF, albeit a small one (+ 5% compared to baseline). When the absorber layers are annealed under a cover, both the highest and lowest efficiencies are achieved depending on the presence of K. It is likely that the local atmosphere created between the absorber layer and the cover is responsible for this observation. The increase in V_{oc} is attributed to an improved pn junction for both exposed and covered cells. The highest efficiencies obtained for the covered cells are due to an even larger increase in V_{oc} . This was attributed to a reduction of the dark/light crossover in addition to the improved pn junction. The change in crossover suggests that the CdS layer is different for the covered samples which could come from changed growth mechanisms. Detailed understanding of the local atmosphere will help to understand what the best atmosphere for a KF-PDT is and how it can affect the CdS growth and pn junction. At last, it has to be mentioned that the standard deviations of the device parameters are rather large for the covered samples. We think this comes from the large inhomogeneity of the lateral KF distribution. This sensitivity to the inhomogeneous KF deposition could be solved by using a different method to add KF, e.g. evaporation or sublimation of KF.

From the various samples, it is observed that the V_{oc} is limited to 640 mV. Similar high V_{oc} values for a GGI of 0.3 have previously only been achieved after passivation of the back contact.^{4,5} SCAPS simulations reveal that after KF treatment recombination at the back contact is limiting the V_{oc} and improvement up to 700 mV can be anticipated when the back contact is passivated. These results show the potential of thinning CIGS to 500 nm, and the importance of the interfaces. The question remains when the absorber layer becomes limiting. Here we achieved top V_{oc} values -compared to thin passivated CIGS cells- using single-stage absorber layers, which are considered to be of lesser quality than 3-stage absorber layers. However, from a manufacturing point of view single-stage co-evaporation remains interesting and it might be that for thin CIGS, in which the diffusion length is less important, single-stage co-evaporated absorber layers are a good option. Implementation of an optimized passivation layer combined with the KF treatment should resolve this question.

Supporting Information

S1: GDOES data of the alkali of the covered sample

S2: J_{sc} values of the different samples

S3: EQE spectra of the covered reference and a KF treated cell

S4: Doping profiles for a covered, exposed and reference cell

S5: Extracted shunt and series resistances from the dark JV measurements for the exposed series

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